

Burkina Faso: Mapping Terrorism

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"If you know your enemies and you know yourself, in a hundred battles you will never be defeated. If you know yourself but not your enemy, for every victory you will also suffer a defeat. If you know neither your enemy nor yourself, you will succumb in every battle."

Sun Tzu, The Art of War

The last case described in this quotation appears to be that of Burkina Faso. Burkina (Sahel) has experienced multiform and intensive terrorist aggressions in recent years, perpetrated by non-state actors whose identity remains imprecisely established.

Considering the number of victims since the current governance, the attack on the general staff headquarters, the methods employed and the intensity of operations, it can be stated unequivocally that Burkina has entered the era of hyper-terrorism, which is growing crescendo, while a marked decline in attacks is observed in the West.

Public opinion and the authorities refer to terrorist organisations and their respective acronyms, without being able to determine, in depth, their true identity or real motivations. One may know the name of an actor without truly knowing them. According to J.-F. Revel, "the terrorist of one is the resistance fighter of the other"; history indeed establishes that entities once qualified as terrorists have, in certain cases, become partners in dialogue, from the PLO through to the Oslo Accords, the KLA until 1998, the ANC declared outlawed in 1960, not to mention hostage releases through negotiation, to cite only these examples.

It should nevertheless be noted that the boundaries between religious terrorism, political terrorism and terrorism of a mafia nature remain indeterminate. Many terrorist groups, operating under the cover of religious, ideological or political motives, appear to be more closely aligned with arms trafficking, drug trafficking or organised crime. In the latter scenario, the ideological profile is foregrounded to mask the real objective. What we are dealing with is a hybrid.

Terrorism is therefore protean in its motivations (religious, ideological, political, separatist or purely criminal) and in its operational spaces, which are transnational, at least within the Sahel. The primary challenge is that of mapping the real profile of the groups (as a people or nation, including non-indigenous populations) and the

second is that of the individual profile, understood through the lens of the psycho- and socioeconomic environment.

A second point concerns the military dimension and the eradication of socioeconomic causes: intellectual awakening, social frustrations and injustices, marginalisations, ethnicisations, segregations, alienations, humiliations, precariousness, stigmatisations, discontent and demographic change, which fuel the radicalisation of these groups and individuals.

A third point is the need to recognise or accept that terrorists have become powers with which informal dialogue can be engaged. Such dialogue, which falls within the realm of diplomacy, can only be established if one masters the interlocutor's background and their demands.

Profiles

Collective Profile

What ideology or "political platform" underpins these massive aggressions and terrorist acts? What are the objectives or demands: territorial independence in embryonic form, religious separatism or other motives? What is the modus operandi: guerrilla warfare and/or terrorism? The orders to close schools and administrative offices, the bombings, assassinations, kidnappings, acts of destruction and sabotage all constitute acts and injunctions that enable the construction of an initial profile.

The multiple attacks without claimed responsibility, and, more recently, the assassination of a Canadian national, yield two indicators: either the groups are, at this stage, disorganised, and therefore too weak to negotiate a ransom; or this constitutes a strong signal indicating that negotiation is not part of their agenda, which is already externally funded.

Kidnapping is an important communication tool for terrorists when they wish to enter into negotiation with the State of origin of the victim or with the authorities of the country in which the abduction takes place. Kidnapping is also a means not only of replenishing funds, but also of conducting exchanges (arms for hostages), generating publicity or exerting pressure aimed at provoking the intervention of foreign governments.

To date, no mapping of the terrorism afflicting Burkina Faso has been established. In view of the number and intensity of attacks, the silence of claimed responsibility, the methods employed (guerrilla warfare and bombing) and the targets (civilians, military personnel and symbols of the State), nothing and no one appears to be spared. It is therefore urgent to uncover, elucidate and identify the objectives of the armed groups, as well as the means at their disposal: arms statistics, intelligence methods and techniques used.

Beyond these initial profiling elements, it is essential to involve social science and statistics researchers in military strategy, in order to better apprehend the socio-conjunctural evolution of the regions concerned: sense of dispossession and social injustice, intellectual and demographic evolution, religious values, etc.

The collection of intelligence through surveys, its centralisation and exploitation make it possible to uncover the unspoken concerns of a community. This exercise can be partially carried out through subtle interviews of local populations regarding their habits and surveillance, adapted to Sahelian realities. Such a survey, at once subtle and conducted at mass scale, makes it possible to identify the unstated intentions of interlocutors, thus constituting what may be termed psycho-strategic intelligence.

Prisoners of war, subjected to psychological work, may over time voluntarily or involuntarily disclose certain information. The background and traceability of neutralised combatants can also provide indicators regarding their identity, origin, place of upbringing, associates and habits. It should be noted that terrorist operations generally require no significant cost and can be conducted by isolated cells or individuals.

Individual Profile, or the Stockholm Syndrome

Beyond the pernicious grievances among Fulani nationals (dispossession and economic exploitation, precariousness, stigmatisation, frustration), the massacre perpetrated by a local traditional militia, the Koglweogo (which went without judicial consequence) has sounded the death knell for peace in the collective consciousness of this community for generations to come.

This community feels abandoned by the central government, perceived as passively complicit, and against which feelings of vengeance (born of the humiliations and massacres endured) may emerge. Thus, the ordinary citizen may be transformed, overnight, into a terrorist actor or sympathiser.

The recruitment of adherents to the terrorist cause is a deliberate strategy: attracting the maximum number of indigenous and non-indigenous supporters, creating new combatants and sympathisers in order to swell the ranks, and thereby forming large armed groups capable of holding their own against regular armies. The frustration stemming from the redistribution of the benefits of subsoil exploitation, injustice and, naturally, the oppression of disadvantaged strata represent the primary causes of rallying, well before the religious factor.

The tragic events of Yirgou have extended the terrorist recruitment capacity in Burkina Faso, among civilians and military personnel alike. For terrorism does not consist solely of acting; it also aims to influence psychologically, to discourage communities and individuals from assisting the Defence and Security Forces in terms of intelligence or early detection, and, worse still, to create new terrorists entirely independent, conditioned solely by a tragic lived experience such as that of

Yirgou. It is here that Revel's observation finds its full substance: "The terrorist of one is the resistance fighter of the other."

The indoctrination of a population that feels oppressed requires no particular effort: it presents itself simply as an awakening of consciousness regarding legitimate self-defence. Burkina Faso has created lifelong enemies among the Koglweogo and lifelong enemies among the Mossi, even though the responsible party is clearly identifiable: not the Mossi, but the Koglweogo, an institution that exists neither in secular culture nor in the Constitution. The penal justice system has remained silent; it has thereby failed in its mission.

Terrorists are not imported; they are motivated (Stockholm Syndrome), internally recruited and supported. Terrorism seeks to demonstrate the limits of the power in place, to convince oppressed individuals that the State, the political system and the army are incapable of protecting the population and its interests, and that a politico-religious change is therefore necessary.

Work on social justice, penal justice and a conjunctural approach aimed at restoring communal peace and peace of mind can reduce the recruitment capacity among individuals not yet committed to a separatist or independence ideology.

Terrorists also recruit through repression, by targeting sections of the population that do not manifest support for their cause. The pedagogical assassinations of dignitaries, resource persons or ordinary citizens, designed to make an impression, serve as examples.

If primacy is accorded to intelligence and the logic of war, the two profiles outlined above imply that beyond the military dimension, this war must integrate the sociocultural and socioeconomic dimensions. In strategic terms, it is therefore necessary to associate experts in social psychology, social economics and statistics with military strategy, since the government's indolence in the face of the Yirgou events caused the army to lose its only chance (popular collaboration) of winning this war in the Sahel.

Dual Strategy: Military and Socioeconomic

Military: The Double Compaoré Pact Broken in 2014

The severing of the Compaoré regime's ties with jihadist movements, combined with the dismantling of the RSP (Presidential Security Regiment), the intelligence service par excellence, undoubtedly constituted the triggering factors behind Burkina Faso's exposure and vulnerability.

The euphoria of the insurrection (much like the coup d'état of Amadou Haya Sanogo in Mali) led to security essentials being sacrificed in favour of political opportunism. The consequence: Burkina Faso is now caught between terrorism and guerrilla

warfare. To compound this situation, successive Ministers of Defence appear to have been appointed by co-optation rather than by competence.

According to the analysis of the moment, beyond the attacks against civilian targets, the modus operandi rests on the principle of "action-reaction": a trap, founded on psycho-strategic manipulation, planned, coordinated and imposed by the adversary. For a modern army (provided that statistics and methods are taken into account), the responses to adversarial intentions could have been better anticipated.

Explosive devices deployed for tactical purposes (luring by a subversive act or ambushing a small convoy) and for strategic purposes (causing a large number of casualties among rescue and security services) generate widespread psychosis and profound emotion. It is precisely this method that most often explains the psychosis and indecision of the military hierarchy when faced with an attack. The war against terrorism is not a standard campaign; it has no temporal, creative or geographical boundaries, hence the need for absolute rigour in its conduct.

The current terrorism in Burkina Faso is hybrid and oversized (in terms of intensity, marking the transition from standard Sahelian terrorism to targeted hyper-terrorism), with state, military, educational, administrative, commercial and civilian targets, as well as a capacity for concealment within the population. This is no longer a generic threat: it is a tailored threat, in view of the geostrategic situation of the country. If Burkina were to falter, a domino effect would occur across several countries in the sub-region.

In such a context, is it opportune or judicious to appoint a Minister of Defence who lacks any training in military tactics and strategy, who is incapable of reading a military map, in a time of war? Such a configuration can only lead to a heavier burden and dysfunction in strategic decision-making (in sum, an inefficient lack of coordination of offensive and defensive operations) for the simple reason that the individual will be incapable of determining which of his military advisers' proposals is most relevant when faced with an urgent situation.

The psychological and geographical diversion of attacks constitutes a form of harassment designed to push uncertainty and fear to the extreme within the ranks. The war against terrorism is always unprecedented, unconventional, and demands great ingenuity in terms of reactivity.

It is the army that is responsible for the security of the territory, not networks of friends nor political family. Its effectiveness, morality and commitment are a reflection of its finest elements. And as the saying goes, "the life of the people and order in the nation are in the hands of the general." The current regime has not yet realised, despite the attack on the general staff headquarters, that Burkina Faso is in a state of war, which should imply a transfer of certain powers from civilian to military authority.

Decentralisation of Command

A decentralisation of command is necessary, as the area is vast and the command structure too heavy to allow for optimal reactivity. What overwhelms the central command is the immensity of the region; yet the solutions lie in exploiting the very nature of that region. A redeployment of military bases along the Sahel borders and to the east of the country is urgent, it being understood that numerical and material superiority of an army does not compensate for moral superiority, although the reverse is possible and highly effective.

Officers must then set the example to galvanise the troops, not as figurehead chiefs, but as prudent and present strategic assistants. On a technical level, the current Minister of Security is competent, and his role must be decisive, as counter-terrorist policing constitutes the proactive nerve of intelligence. However, given the generational difference, legitimate questions may be raised regarding the criteria for selecting his personnel.

Communications and Cyber Defence

A war is never won on the basis of excessive pride, propagandist and ostentatious declarations on social networks, naive hope placed in a single personality, or on the moral support of the population alone, but on professionalism, ingenuity, the morale of the troops and diplomacy.

New strategic and technological thinking must be conceived and implemented, ranging from cyber defence to the realities of the field. Terrorist networks make use of modern communication and information techniques; cyberterrorism is also a common practice in the preparation of attacks and other operations.

It must be clearly understood that terrorists master the ultra-modern technologies of telecommunications (interception, jamming, manipulation of communications, localisation and sabotage of computer networks), services that can be provided from abroad according to the sponsor. Computer intelligence does not need informants within the regular army to intercept messages and communications, whether electronic or telephonic.

Remote sensing, radar trucks and other methods, secure military telecommunications, cyber strategy and cyber espionage (notably internet profiling software) are important parameters. Have the available technological methods and applications been truly examined, given that China is very advanced in the field of remote sensing? An effective army relies eighty per cent on intelligence, as the arsenal is only useful once the target has been determined. The intelligence apparatus must therefore be Sahelised.

Sahelising

To Sahelise is to rethink and reform the intelligence system and its methods with the assistance of academics in the social and psychological sciences. Sahelising intelligence also means organising mass-scale espionage, transforming military personnel into farmers, shepherds, shopkeepers, teachers, etc., for years at a time.

It means recruiting and training individuals already active in other spheres: taxi drivers, farmers, shepherds, teachers, street vendors, couriers, shoe shiners, etc.

The Burkinabe army does not sufficiently take into account the Sahelian scale, which is not a conventional theatre of war; it always reacts without analysing or drawing lessons from previous assaults: it is the equivalent of planting a lemon tree and waiting for mangoes.

The conventional method has demonstrated its incapacities and its limits in winning this war. In sum, it is the equivalent of using a screwdriver to drive a nail, when what is needed is a hammer.

Infiltration in all its forms is a risk worth taking: many communities, movements or individuals have been funded by intelligence services in order to bring about the dismantling of adversaries. A protection or amnesty programme always accompanies such approaches.

The strategy for each terrain lies within its own nature. It is necessary to examine mobility strategies adapted to the terrain (infantry battalions) while keeping armoured logistics and communications a few kilometres in the background. Since the infantry can only operate over a few kilometres, air power and motorised units, capable of rapid deployment, provide relief after infantry sweeps during enemy retreat or the detection of attackers, all within an inter-service coordination framework (air-land).

A canine brigade is essential: no one can corrupt a dog, faithful in detection and alerting.

Beyond the military offensive, it is indispensable to conduct a strategic-cultural one, lightly inspired by the Millet system under the Ottoman Empire: cultural and religious tolerance, and adapted administration.

Socioeconomic

On the intellectual level, the region is experiencing a revolution of consciousness, which legitimately aspires to the redistribution of wealth and seeks greater transparency in the management of subsoil exploitation. Furthermore, galloping demographic growth generates increasing inequalities in social, infrastructural and administrative conditions.

The mindset of the numerous younger generation is awakening to its legitimate rights, unlike previous generations, which were less numerous and less educated. The MNLA illustrates this postulate.

Cultural identity, civilisational values, spiritual values and socioeconomic justice are thus becoming demands, even if they remain silent for the time being. This community no longer shares the values of a governmental system perceived as predatory; a strong desire for identity belonging and the defence of community interests becomes the creed against pauperisation. This is precisely what Mali failed to consider with regard to the Tuareg; and the aftermath is well known.

To address these inequalities and deteriorations, mining companies can play a preponderant role. Unfortunately, the State's inaction in the face of the Koglweogo's exactions has deepened these grievances. The village of Yirgou has now become a natural recruitment lever (for combatants and sympathisers) among a broad segment of the Fulani population, children, women and men alike, driven by a desire for vengeance that may manifest in lone-wolf type actions. The religious, cultural and political instrumentalisation, amplified by the media coverage of the tragedy, has a long future ahead of it.

Organised crime (another natural ally of terrorism) will also see a resurgence, as weapons circulate. Economic crime linked to raw materials, drug trafficking, smuggling and armed robbery are a logical consequence in zones of terrorist influence, as these groups require sources of funding.

A vast social programme, free of bureaucracy, is imperative.

A committee for the prevention of indoctrination and psychosocial de-indoctrination, as well as the training of 'Franco-Arab' imams and the distribution of illustrated brochures in local languages, notably via radio, represent a long-term undertaking.

A programme of protection and amnesty for intelligence collaborators, infiltrated individuals or defectors (who must subsequently be relocated from the region with financial compensation) is necessary. Collaborators and infiltrated agents must present a specific profile: unmarried or socially isolated, with no highly visible family ties, and in a situation of idleness. These are individuals trained discreetly on the basis of their habitual occupations: an essential component of the Sahelisation of intelligence methods.

The challenges cannot be addressed solely through the repressive and military dimension, for as Carlos Marighella observed, "the State, in response to terrorism, has no choice but to impose restrictive and increasingly unpopular security measures that impact on the population."

And for national salvation and the well-being of the population, dialogue constitutes an option for obtaining truces, de-escalation or concessions.

Diplomacy and Dialogue

Prolonged attacks exhaust the population, families, the economy, political consensus and the nation's international media image, weaken the regime and may lead to popular revolt. The situation is clear: hyper-terrorism in Burkina Faso constitutes an outlaw power, versatile, diverse and undulating: a Hydra, in sum; when one head is cut, two grow back automatically. Unofficial diplomacy is therefore required, as Western nations practise in order to save hostages' lives, without ever officially acknowledging it.

A confidential cabinet of specialised individuals must be created for this purpose, associating mining companies and sons of the region. The terrorist has only his ideology to defend, sometimes not even his life. The State, for its part, is responsible for the lives of its population, their well-being, their education, the integrity of the territory, the protection of infrastructure, peace and justice.

The war must above all be won through a policy of stabilisation in Burkina Faso.

Invest for maximum political gain, so as to target minimum military cost, in pursuit of lasting peace: to vanquish and to convince. A bad settlement is better than a good lawsuit, as the saying goes; in other words, diplomacy must always accompany a war with uncertain outcomes; this was the strategy of the previous regime. To negotiate is also to offer the enemy an exit; otherwise, he fights to the death. The Prophet Muhammad (SAW) always combined diplomacy with war, and a good Muslim cannot exempt himself from this.

A sailing vessel (the State) cannot navigate on four winds simultaneously; a judicious choice must be made, however painful. The challenges are numerous and urgent: the economy, security, social unrest and development. In other words: no wind is favourable to a ship without a destination.

To further compound the situation, the Mossi traditional chieftaincy and the Koglweogo (also of Mossi allegiance) appear to manage the entirety of the country according to their own rules, which suggests a residual tendency toward Mossi customary governance of Burkinabe territory. This generates frustrations that inhibit the voluntary impulses of the Sahel's traditional chiefs, who, according to certain sources, maintained good relations with Mr M. Chafi.

The tone and cadence of an ethno-political influence are thus set. The unilateral application of recourse to a traditional chief on national matters, and the creation of the Koglweogo, carry ethnocentric undertones: a pernicious but latent malaise that simmers.

This practice tends to confer a national and political supremacy, silent but manifest, founded upon the Mossi traditional chieftaincy, which feeds frustration among other communities and minorities. This observation generates social divisions, since the ethnic chief of the other is not one's own, and his commitments and decisions are not either.

It will be necessary to accord legitimate voice and standing to the dignitaries of each region, according to their respective jurisdictions and attributions, and not at the level of the Burkinabe nation as a whole, and this applies to all. To accept a culturally differentiated administration, should the majority of the population concerned demand it. To confer a control power over the redistribution of wealth and to examine communal-administrative federalism.

Concessions may then be made to attenuate the consequences of the country's current economic and reputational decline. Without prior security, investors will not

risk the lives of their employees. Which tourist, today, would choose Burkina Faso as a destination?

While taking into account the sensitivities arising from the damage caused by the 2014 Insurrection and the Diendéré coup d'état, it must be recognised that the house is in peril. If granting amnesty or pardoning certain individuals could restore peace (even momentarily), then the step must be taken. Politics is like a game of chess: when the king faces certain impasse, it is capture that seals his fate.

As an immediate but radical endogenous solution, Burkina Faso will need to pass through a sacred union of all its forces, omitting neither the psychosocial nor the socioeconomic dimension: integrating apolitical or repentant elements of the former RSP as scouts, to share their intelligence expertise within the corps; during this reconfiguration, sending elements for training in Chad and other countries confronting the same phenomena; recruiting indigenous trackers.

Granting amnesty to dignitaries of the previous regime (prior to the Transition) in exchange for a solemn commitment to participate in negotiations, as a factor of de-escalation. And, difficult to implement under fire: a total, apolitical and technical overhaul of the army, drawing upon Burkinabe military experts from international systems (notably the United Nations) to identify weaknesses, assess competencies and determine needs.

Finally, to restore socioeconomic justice across the entire territory and to establish an amnesty and protection regime for repentant individuals.

As for exogenous solutions, the most immediate and viable is the engagement of the Chadian army, which, with the best will in the world, cannot sacrifice itself as nationals would.

It will have been understood that this text has deliberately refrained from elaborating upon sensitive military information.

War or the Table, the Table and War: the Table endures at every conclusion. Such is the dialectic, for the war must also be won in hearts and minds. If Serval in Mali became Barkhane, now accompanied by MNLA dignitaries, it is through the fruit of dialogue.

Notes and References

* OSR-Terrorism Burkina Faso: Open Situation Room is a German practice allowing citizens and experts of all backgrounds to express their views on current national or international issues.

** Refer to the Larousse dictionary, the lexical comparison of the word which is neutral in origin in English (and in German) in relation to its French equivalent, and finally to the works of Goncourt or Beauvoir.

*** Mohamed Ag Aharib, spokesman for the Ansar Dine movement, in Ouagadougou: "If negotiations are engaged with the Malian authorities, one can consider the ways and means by

which terrorism, drug trafficking and foreign movements can be eliminated." Principal movements targeted: Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM).

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